

1 **Effect of metal loading on the CO₂ methanation: A comparison between**
2 **alumina supported Ni and Ru catalysts**

3 Adrián Quindimil^a, Unai De-La-Torre^a, Beñat Pereda-Ayo, Arantxa Davó-Quiñonero^b, Esther Bailón-
4 García^b, Dolores Lozano-Castelló^b, José A. González-Marcos^a, Agustín Bueno-López^b, Juan R. González-
5 Velasco^{a*}

6 ^a*Chemical Engineering Department, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of the Basque Country*
7 *UPV/EHU, Barrio Sarriena, s/n, E48940 – Leioa, Bizkaia, Spain*

8 ^b*Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Alicante, Carretera de San Vicente s/n. E03080-*
9 *Alicante, Spain.*

10

11

12 *Corresponding author: juanra.gonzalezvelasco@ehu.es (Juan R. González-Velasco)

13

14 **Abstract**

15 The hydrogenation of CO₂ into CH₄ from H₂ produced by renewable energy is considered an
16 interesting alternative in order to promote the development of such green energies. In the
17 present work, the effect of Ni and Ru loadings on the catalytic performance of alumina-
18 supported catalysts is studied for CO₂ methanation reaction. All catalysts were prepared by
19 wetness incipient impregnation, characterized by several techniques (N₂-physisorption, CO₂-
20 TPD, XRD, H₂-chemisorption, XPS and H₂-TPR) and evaluated for CO₂ methanation in a fixed
21 bed reactor at *GHSV* = 10,000 h⁻¹ and $W / F_{\text{CO}_2}^0 = 4.7$ (g cat.) h mol⁻¹. Characterization results
22 showed that addition of increasing loadings of Ni and Ru lead to the formation of both CO₂
23 adsorption and H₂ dissociation active sites, which are necessary to carry out CO₂
24 hydrogenation into methane. Easily reducible ruthenium was dispersed on γ -Al₂O₃ in form of
25 large agglomerates, whereas Ni was better dispersed presenting a great interaction with the
26 support. 12% Ni and 4% Ru resulted to be the optimal contents providing metal surfaces of 5.1
27 and 0.6 m² g⁻¹, *T*₅₀ values of 340 and 310 °C and activity being quite stable for 24h-on-stream.
28 In terms of turnover frequency (*TOF*), 4%Ru/Al₂O₃ catalyst was quite more efficient than
29 12%Ni/Al₂O₃, probably due to a greater ability of ruthenium to dissociate hydrogen. The
30 apparent activation energies for alumina supported Ni and Ru were 129 and 84 kJ mol⁻¹,
31 respectively.

32

33

34

35 *Keywords:* CO₂ methanation, metal loading, ruthenium, nickel, particle size

36

37

Highlights

- Increasing loading of Ni and Ru increases the surface basicity and forms new CO₂ adsorption sites.
- High calcination temperature leads to an increase of RuO₂ particle size and formation of inert Ni species.
- Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts present high metal-support interaction, so that only a relative amount of metal is active for CO₂ methanation.
- Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts are more efficient than Ni/Al₂O₃ in hydrogen dissociation; TOF of the former is about ten times than TOF of Ni catalysts.
- Optimal behavior was found for 12% Ni and 4% Ru, which provide metal surfaces of 5.1 and 0.6 m² g⁻¹, respectively.

38 1. Introduction

39 Progressive reduction of carbon dioxide emissions, considered as a route to decrease the
40 impact of greenhouse gases (GHG) on climate, is one of the major environmental challenges of
41 today's society. The replacement of fossil energy by renewable energy sources is the best
42 option to tackle that challenge. The main downside is that renewable energy such as wind and
43 solar is fluctuating, i.e., in many cases, the power from electric generators does not match the
44 energy demand. Besides, renewable energy power installed worldwide is far from enough to
45 meet the global energy demand. Thus, the development and incorporation of alternative
46 transition technologies into the current energy system is necessary [1].

47 In order to control CO₂ emissions and stabilize CO₂ atmospheric concentration, transition
48 changes are needed in the current energy system. Nowadays, there are two main strategies: (i)
49 CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) and (ii) CO₂ recycling. Although CCS technology is viable in
50 reducing CO₂ emissions, it has some disadvantages such as the necessity of a site for CO₂
51 sequestration close to CO₂ source or the costly transportation of captured CO₂ to the storage
52 site, which reduces the efficiency of the process [2]. Nevertheless, CO₂ recycling is considered
53 a complementary and interesting alternative to CCS. Through this process, CO₂, the major
54 atmospheric pollutant, can be converted into chemical compounds (mainly urea, salicylic acid
55 and polycarbonates) or fuels [2–4]. Considering that the amount of carbon emitted from fossil
56 fuels combustion is 100 times higher than that used for synthesis of chemicals, it seems more
57 reasonable to convert CO₂ into different energy vectors such as methane, methanol and
58 dimethylether [4–7].

59 Among the different conversion alternatives, CO₂ methanation is thermodynamically the most
60 favorable reaction. Carbon dioxide, captured from combustion or other processes, can be
61 combined with H₂ generated from renewable energy and catalytically converted into methane
62 or synthetic natural gas (SNG) according to the Sabatier reaction:

64 In that way, not only anthropogenic CO₂ emissions are reduced, but also surplus renewable
65 energy is stored in form of SNG that could be easily transported by the current gas grid.

66 Generally, catalysts used in CO₂ methanation consists of group VIII transition metals (active
67 phase) supported over mesoporous solids. γ -Alumina has proven to be an effective support to
68 carry out CO₂ methanation [8, 9]. This support provides high specific surface area (100-250 m²
69 g⁻¹), contains surface basicity (hydroxyl groups) for CO₂ activation and over which the active
70 phase can be dispersed. Among group VIII metals, Ni and Ru have been the most used [10].

71 These metals, in their reduced state, are able to effectively dissociate the hydrogen that reacts
72 with CO₂ adsorbed on the support. Ni-based catalysts have been extensively investigated
73 because of their high activity and low price [11–15], whereas Ru-based catalysts due to their
74 excellent activity and selectivity at low temperature [16–20]. Therefore, a catalytic component
75 is required to activate CO₂ for a further reduction, as the aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃), and also a
76 metal component (here Ni or Ru) that is able to dissociate H₂. Providing that both
77 functionalities are present, activity, selectivity and deactivation of the catalyst seem to be
78 significantly dependent on the metal particle size [14, 16]. It seems that Ni-based catalysts
79 require high metal loadings and are easily deactivated by sintering or coke deposition, in a
80 more extension than Ru based catalysts, which in turn are much more expensive. In some
81 cases, a third promoter component is used to improve metal dispersion and CO₂ adsorption
82 [18, 19, 21, 22] or to avoid fast deactivation by sintering and fouling [12, 23].

83 In recent literature, there are many works that report separately the catalytic performance of
84 Ni-based and Ru-based formulations at different operation conditions, which makes a direct
85 comparison between the activity of both metals difficult. Previously, Garbarino et al. [8]
86 studied and compared the activation, catalytic performance and stability of commercial
87 3%Ru/Al₂O₃ and 20%Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts, observing that the performance of the former was
88 better than that of the latter. For this study, we have prepared both series of Al₂O₃-supported
89 Ni and Ru catalysts with loadings that assure metal particle sizes to be effective to dissociate
90 H₂ and activate CO₂ reduction. The aim is to compare the activity of supported Ni and Ru and
91 to study the effect of metal loading.

92

93 **2. Experimental**

94 2.1 Catalysts preparation

95 In order to synthesize alumina-supported catalysts with different Ni and Ru contents, a simple,
96 fast and well-known preparation method such as wetness incipient impregnation was used.
97 This method consisted of adding the previously dissolved Ni or Ru precursor on a commercial
98 γ -Al₂O₃ (*Saint-Gobain NorPro 6173*) driving the solute into the pores by capillary forces. The
99 employed metal precursors were Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (*Sigma Aldrich, 99.99%*) and Ru(NO)(NO₃)₃ in
100 diluted nitric acid (*Sigma Aldrich, Ru = 1.5% w/v*).

101 In total, 5 Ni-based catalysts were prepared varying the Ni nominal content from 4 to 20 wt.%.
102 Firstly, a volume of Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O aqueous solution 1.2 times larger than catalysts pore
103 volume was impregnated dropwise over Al₂O₃ ($V_p = 0.6 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$). Secondly, the impregnated

104 samples were dried during 6 h at 60 °C and further 6 h at 120 °C. Finally, the catalysts were
105 calcined at 500 °C for 4 h with a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹.

106 Regarding Ru-based catalysts, 5 additional samples were synthesized by successive
107 impregnations, varying Ru loading from 1 to 5 wt.%. Due to Ru precursor solubility limitations,
108 a maximum 1% of Ru was incorporated in each impregnation. In line with Ni based catalysts,
109 Ru(NO)(NO₃)₃ solution volume 1.2 times greater than V_p was impregnated, after adjusting the
110 pH of the solution to 1 by acid nitric addition. After each impregnation, samples were dried
111 during 6 h at 60 °C followed by extra 6 h at 120 °C and calcined at 400 °C during 4 h with a
112 heating rate of 1 °C min⁻¹. These calcination temperatures for Ni and Ru catalysts were
113 previously optimized by thermogravimetric studies varying the temperature from room
114 temperature to 1000 °C, as the minimum temperature for decomposing each precursor.

115 2.2. Characterization techniques

116 *N₂ adsorption-desorption*. Textural properties of the samples were determined from N₂
117 adsorption-desorption isotherms measured at -196 °C using a *Micromeritics TRISTAR II 3020*
118 instrument. Pore volumes were calculated by t-plot method while pore size distribution of
119 mesoporous solids was determined using BJH method. The samples were previously degassed
120 overnight under N₂ flow.

121 *CO₂ Temperature Programmed Desorption (CO₂-TPD)*. Surface basicity and basic sites
122 distribution were analyzed by TPD-MS studies. Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument was
123 used coupled to a *MKS Cirrus* mass spectrometer. First of all, Ni/Al₂O₃ and Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts
124 were reduced under 5%H₂/Ar flow for 60 min at 500 °C and 30 min at 300 °C, respectively.
125 Then, CO₂ adsorption step was performed at 50 °C by feeding 50 cm³ STP/min of 5%CO₂/He
126 flow until saturation. Thereafter, the samples were flushed out with helium for 60 min to
127 remove weakly adsorbed CO₂ from the surface. Finally, desorption was carried out from 50 to
128 850 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The CO₂ desorption was continuously monitored with
129 a mass spectrometer.

130 *X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)*. Crystalline phases of alumina supported Ni and Ru catalysts were
131 identified by XRD on a PANalytical Xpert PRO diffractometer with Cu Kα radiation (λ = 1.5418
132 Å) and Ni filter. The operating conditions were 40 kV and 40 mA and diffractograms were
133 recorded from 5 to 70° 2θ with 0.02° per second sampling interval. PANalytical X'pert
134 HighScore specific software was used for data treatment and JCPDS database was used to
135 interpret the diffractograms. On the other hand, the thermogravimetric studies were
136 carried out in a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer operating at 30 kV and 20 mA, equipped

137 with a Cu tube ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$), a Vantec-1 PSD detector, and an Anton Parr HTK2000 high-
138 temperature furnace. The powder patterns were recorded in 2θ steps of 0.033° in the $15 \leq 2\theta$
139 ≤ 70 range, counting for 2 s per step (total time for each temperature was 1 h). Data sets were
140 recorded from 30 to 1010 °C every 20 °C with $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ heating rate.

141 *Hydrogen chemisorption.* The dispersion of active sites was measured by H_2 chemisorption
142 employing a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 apparatus. Prior to the experiments, $\text{Ni/Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and
143 $\text{Ru/Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts were reduced with pure H_2 for 2 h at 500 °C and 350 °C, respectively. After
144 that, the samples were degasified at the same temperature for 90 min. For both formulations,
145 the adsorption isotherms were recorded at 35 °C varying the pressure between 50 and 450
146 mmHg. Adsorption stoichiometries of $\text{Ni/H} = 1$ and $\text{Ru/H} = 1$ were assumed.

147 *Hydrogen Temperature Programmed Reduction (H_2 -TPR).* The reducibility of $\text{Ni/Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and
148 $\text{Ru/Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts was studied by H_2 -TPR tests. The experiments were performed on a
149 *Micromeritics AutoChem 2920* instrument. In the case of $\text{Ni/Al}_2\text{O}_3$, these were firstly pre-
150 treated at 350 °C for 30 min under Ar flow in order to remove adsorbed H_2O and CO_2 . The
151 reducing gas flow was $50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ STP/min}$ of $5\% \text{H}_2/\text{Ar}$ and the temperature was increased from 30
152 to 900 °C with a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. The water formed during reduction was trapped
153 using a cold trap and the hydrogen consumption was continuously monitored with a TCD
154 detector.

155 *X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy.* The catalysts were characterised before and after the
156 catalytic tests. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis was performed by using a K-
157 Alpha spectrophotometer (Thermo-Scientific) with a high-resolution monochromator. The
158 binding energy was adjusted using the C 1s transition, appearing at 284.6 eV. Binding energy
159 values measured are accurate to $\pm 0.2 \text{ eV}$. Oxidation states of Ni and Ru, as well as, surface
160 atomic composition were determined by means of this technique.

161 2.3. CO_2 methanation experiments

162 CO_2 methanation reactions were performed in a downflow fixed bed reactor ($D_{\text{in}} = 9 \text{ mm}$) and
163 the product distribution was analyzed with a gas chromatograph (*Agilent 490 micro GC*). Ni
164 and Ru based catalysts were first reduced for 1 h under $20\% \text{H}_2/\text{He}$ flow ($300 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ STP/min}$) at
165 500 °C and 300 °C, respectively. After cooling down to 200 °C in inert gas, the reaction mixture
166 was fed to the reactor with a 5:1:1.5 $\text{H}_2:\text{CO}_2:\text{He}$ molar ratio. The catalytic performance of the
167 prepared catalysts was studied between 200 and 500 °C, in steps of 25 °C, with a heating rate
168 of $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ between each step. The He, H_2 , CO_2 , CH_4 and CO concentrations at the reactor exit
169 were monitored once steady state was reached.

170 Activity tests were carried out at atmospheric pressure with 0.5 g of catalyst ($d_p = 0.3-0.5$ mm).
 171 The catalyst particles were diluted to 50% with quartz particles in order to improve heat
 172 transfer. In these conditions, $GHSV$ and $W / F_{CO_2}^0$ were $10,000 \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $4.67 \text{ (g cat.) h mol}^{-1}$,
 173 respectively. Additionally, the effect of space time ($W / F_{CO_2}^0 = 0$) on CO_2 conversion was studied
 174 varying space velocity from $10,000 \text{ h}^{-1}$ to $40,000 \text{ h}^{-1}$ at different reaction temperatures.
 175 CO_2 conversion (X_{CO_2}), CH_4 yield (Y_{CH_4}) and CO yield (Y_{CO}) were calculated as:

$$176 \quad X_{CO_2} = \frac{F_{CO_2}^{in} - F_{CO_2}^{out}}{F_{CO_2}^{in}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$177 \quad Y_{CH_4} = \frac{F_{CH_4}^{out}}{F_{CO_2}^{in}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$178 \quad Y_{CO} = \frac{F_{CO}^{out}}{F_{CO_2}^{in}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

179 Activity of catalysts is also compared by T_{50} , which represents the temperature at which the
 180 catalyst achieves CO_2 conversion of 50% ($X_{CO_2} = 50\%$).

181

182 **3. Results**

183 3.1. Characterization

184 3.1.1. Surface properties

185 Figure S1 shows the N_2 physisorption isotherms as well as the pore size distribution of alumina
 186 support used for the prepared catalysts. As it can be noticed, the shape of the isotherms is
 187 characteristic of mesoporous solid: a great quantity of N_2 is adsorbed at intermediate relative
 188 pressures by multilayer filling with a hysteresis loop at relative pressures higher than 0.65
 189 (type IV isotherm and H2 hysteresis loop according to IUPAC). Specific surface area, mesopore
 190 volume and average pore size values for fresh $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, compiled in Table 1, present values of
 191 $214 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, $0.563 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and 10.1 nm , respectively, which are high enough to perform the
 192 impregnation of large metal loading, allowing the present study concerning the effect of active
 193 phase loading.

194

194 **FIGURE S1**

195 Textural properties of alumina-supported Ni and Ru catalysts are also summarized in Table 1.
 196 As it can be noticed, the raise of Ni content from 4 to 20% leads to a gradual decrease of

197 specific surface area and mesopore volume from $214 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ to $131 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and from $0.563 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$
198 1 to $0.326 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively. These changes in textural properties are attributed to partial
199 blockage/filling of alumina mesopores with NiO aggregates and/or to partial collapse of the
200 mesoporous structure [11, 14, 24]. On the other hand, similar trends are observed when
201 varying Ru loading.

202

TABLE 1

203 Additionally, the effect of Ni and Ru incorporation on the surface basicity was studied by
204 means of CO_2 -TPD. Figure 1 shows the CO_2 -TPD profiles for $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and for the catalysts with
205 the highest contents of Ru and Ni, i.e., 5%Ru/ Al_2O_3 and 20%Ni/ Al_2O_3 . As it can be observed, the
206 prepared samples contain different CO_2 adsorption sites with different strength. According to
207 desorption temperature or chemical bond strength, basic sites can be classified into weak ($T <$
208 $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), medium ($T = 150\text{-}350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and strong ($T > 350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) [14, 25]. On the one hand, it can be
209 observed that bare alumina presents a single desorption peak at $105 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, attributed to CO_2
210 desorption from weak Bronsted OH^- groups [26]. On the other hand, the new CO_2 desorption
211 peaks observed for 20%Ni/ Al_2O_3 and 5%Ru/ Al_2O_3 catalysts indicate that Ni and Ru addition
212 leads to the formation of new basic sites with different strength. 20%Ni/ Al_2O_3 presents a new
213 CO_2 desorption peak at $275 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, associated with decomposition of bidentate carbonate from
214 medium-strength basic sites [15], whereas 5%Ru/ Al_2O_3 catalyst shows a CO_2 desorption peak
215 at $425 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, attributed to decomposition of monodentate carbonate from strong basic sites [27].
216 The CO_2 surface density quantification obtained from integration of MS 44 signal is also shown
217 in Table 1. While the CO_2 surface density of bare alumina is $0.32 \text{ } \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$, the addition of
218 increasing contents of Ni and Ru rises this value up to 0.5 and $0.42 \text{ } \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$, respectively.
219 Therefore, it can be concluded that Ni and Ru impregnation not only results in the formation of
220 new type of basic sites, but also in an increase of surface basicity.

221 This increase of surface basicity with addition of both Ni and Ru could also theoretically be
222 explained in terms of electronegativity. The electronegativity values of the elements that
223 participate in CO_2 adsorption are 1.6, 1.9, 2.3 and 3.5 for Al, Ni, Ru and O, respectively. These
224 values indicate that surface O^{2-} and OH^- groups linked to Al must contain higher negative
225 charge density (lower basicity) than those attached to Ni and Ru. Thus, differences in
226 electronegativity show that the involved 3 metals transfer negative charge density to surface
227 O^{2-} following the sequence: $\text{Al} > \text{Ni} > \text{Ru}$. Therefore, considering that CO_2 is an acid gas with a
228 high negative charge density, the sites with the highest CO_2 adsorption capacity (and the
229 lowest negative charge density) correspond to O^{2-} (and OH^- if applicable) linked to Ru, followed
230 by those linked to Ni and finally those bound to Al.

231

FIGURE 1

232 3.1.2. Crystallinity and metallic dispersion

233 Crystalline phases of reduced catalysts were identified by X-ray diffraction. XRD patterns of
234 alumina supported catalysts with increasing Ni and Ru contents are shown in Figures 2a and
235 2b, respectively.

236

FIGURE 2

237 In all cases, XRD peaks can be observed at 37.7, 45.8 and 66.8° 2 θ , corresponding to gamma-
238 alumina (311), (400) and (440) diffraction planes, respectively (PDF 01-079-1558). These broad
239 peaks together with an elevated XRD signal background point out that this γ -Al₂O₃ is rather an
240 amorphous than a crystalline solid, which makes the identification of crystalline nano-particles
241 more difficult due to peaks overlapping. In fact, for Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts, the presence of
242 crystalline Ni phases was only detected for catalysts with Ni contents higher than 8%. NiO was
243 identified for calcined catalysts [9] (Figure S2) and the appearance of XRD peaks at 44.3, 51.7
244 and 76.1° 2 θ revealed the formation of elemental Ni in reduced catalysts [12]. However, the
245 presence of NiAl₂O₄ (peaks located at 37.0, 45.0 and 65.5° 2 θ) could not be identified, since it
246 contains the same spatial group with a similar cell parameter of Al₂O₃ (PDF 00-010-0339).

247 Both crystallite sizes and Ni dispersion are summarized in Table 2. The XRD patterns of
248 catalysts with Ni content lower than 12% showed similar diffraction pattern to original Al₂O₃
249 (not shown), probably due to a high dispersion of Ni species (crystallite sizes lower than 5 nm).
250 Therefore, Ni crystallite sizes could be only estimated by Scherrer equation for 12, 16 and 20%
251 Ni loaded catalysts. In all cases, Ni crystallite sizes lower than the average pore size of Al₂O₃
252 (10.1 nm, see Table 1) were observed, which suggests that Ni could be located inside the pores
253 of the catalytic support. It can be observed that dispersion values obtained by H₂-
254 chemisorption match with the trend observed by XRD: the Ni crystallite size estimated by XRD
255 grows from <5 to 7.3 nm, whereas dispersion is reduced from 38 to 11% with the increase of
256 Ni loading. As will be seen later not all nickel can be reduced or is activated after reduction
257 pretreatment for 1 h at 500 °C and therefore, we refer to the dispersion of nickel reducible at
258 those conditions.

259 In the case of Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts, diffraction peaks at 28.0, 35.1 and 54.2° 2 θ were observed in
260 calcined catalysts, characteristic of tetragonal RuO₂ [18, 19] (Figure S2). After reduction
261 pretreatment at 300 °C, new XRD peaks were detected at 38.4, 42.2 and 44.0° 2 θ confirming
262 the presence of ruthenium in reduced state (PDF 00-006-0663). As it can be clearly observed,
263 the intensity of the peaks grows with the increase of ruthenium content from 1 to 5%. The

264 markedly more intense XRD peaks of hexagonal Ru compared to those of cubic Ni are due to
265 higher crystallinity and crystallite sizes, which have also been estimated by Scherrer equation
266 and values are also summarized in Table 2. Note that Ru crystallite size increases from 7.4 to
267 12.1 nm, suggesting a small decrease in active phase dispersion. This trend is in line with H₂
268 chemisorption results: Ru dispersion slightly decreases from 5.5 to 3.9% as metallic content
269 increases from 1 to 5%. Then, the lowest dispersion of 5%Ru/Al₂O₃ catalyst may be associated
270 with the presence of larger Ru particles formed by agglomeration of several Ru nano-crystals.

271

TABLE 2

272 In order to determine the effect of temperature on the crystallinity of Ni/Al₂O₃ and Ru/Al₂O₃
273 samples, additional thermodiffractometric studies were done. Figure 3a shows a waterfall of
274 XRD patterns of 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst measured between 30 and 1010 °C. The variations in
275 intensity and position of the diffraction peaks with temperature are related to changes in the
276 sample crystallinity or to the formation/disappearance of crystalline nickel phases. In fact, the
277 unique peaks that remain unchanged in the whole temperature range are those assigned to
278 inevitable diffraction of the platinum sample holder, at 39.7, 46.2 and 67.4° 2θ. Note that the
279 color of the sample changed with temperature following this sequence: from gray to greenish-
280 gray, from greenish-gray to greenish-blue and from greenish-blue to blue. In the 30 - 310 °C
281 temperature range, only the characteristic XRD peaks of Al₂O₃ were detected, suggesting that
282 higher temperature is needed for the formation of Ni crystalline phases. However, from 310 to
283 610 °C the development of a broad band can be observed at 62.9° 2θ, which is tentatively
284 attributed to highly dispersed greenish-gray NiO. Finally, above 610 °C NiO characteristic peaks
285 disappearance is detected, followed by the formation of more intense peak at 59.7° 2θ,
286 assigned to blue NiAl₂O₄ [27, 28], being more crystalline than highly dispersed NiO. Note that
287 above 710 °C, the peak at 37° 2θ gains in intensity, as a result of NiAl₂O₄ spinel formation
288 contribution. Therefore, it seems that the formation of spinel takes place at temperatures
289 above 600 °C and considering that Ni/Al₂O₃ samples were calcined at 500 °C, the presence of
290 considerable amount of NiAl₂O₄ in the prepared catalysts seems unlikely.

291

FIGURE 3

292 On the other hand, the XRD patterns waterfall of 3%Ru/Al₂O₃ catalyst is shown in Figure 3b. In
293 this case, the presence of Ru crystalline phase (RuO₂) is detected at temperatures above 230 °C
294 and the XRD intensity at 28, 35 and 54.2° 2θ clearly rises with temperature up to 800 °C
295 indicating the increasing formation of RuO₂ tetragonal nano-crystals. At temperatures between
296 810-1010 °C, however, the XRD intensity significantly drops, which indicates the disappearance

297 of RuO₂ probably due to the formation of volatile oxides (RuO_x) [17]. Noteworthy, the size of
298 the nano-crystals remains stable (≈ 20 nm) up to 500 °C and afterwards exponentially grows
299 until 60 nm, suggesting a notable decrease of Ru dispersion for temperatures above 500 °C.
300 Therefore, this confirms that the calcination temperature of 400 °C seems to be enough to
301 form crystalline RuO₂ as Ru precursor and avoid an excessive growing of the crystallites.

302 3.1.3. Analysis of Ni and Ru species nature by XPS and H₂-TPR

303 In order to study the atomic surface composition of prepared catalysts and the nature of
304 surface Ni and Ru species, XPS characterization was carried out. A certain amount of carbon,
305 attributed to atmospheric CO₂ adsorption, was detected by XPS on the surface of all catalysts
306 (between 12 and 15%). Therefore, a direct analysis of the quantitative results of the surface
307 composition is complex and more relevant information is obtained by analyzing the ratio of
308 concentrations between elements. Figures 4a and 4b show the effect of metal loading on
309 surface Ni/Al and Ru/Al atomic ratios of fresh and used (catalytically tested) samples. It should
310 be noted that auxiliary lines in both Figures display a proportional evolution of Ni/Al and Ru/Al
311 with metallic contents, i.e., considering that metallic content does not affect the dispersion.

312

FIGURE 4

313 In Figure 4a, it can be observed that in both cases the amount of surface Ni increases with the
314 total amount of Ni. However, the surface Ni/Al ratios are below the auxiliary line, which
315 suggests a certain decrease in Ni dispersion (see Figure 4a). These results are consistent with
316 XRD results, where an increase of Ni particle size with the metal loading was observed. Note
317 that the Ni/Al ratios are lower in the used catalysts compared to the fresh ones, indicating
318 sintering during the catalytic tests. The impregnation of different amounts of Ru, however, has
319 a different effect on Ru/Al surface atomic ratio (see Figure 4b). In this case, the amount of
320 surface Ru also increases with Ru content; but unlike the Ni/Al ratios, the Ru/Al ratios follow
321 the auxiliary line. This indicates that Ru dispersion does not vary considerably with the increase
322 of metal loading from 1 to 5%. In fact, similar particle sizes of Ru were observed by H₂-
323 chemisorption indicating the same trend. Finally, observe that the Ru/Al ratios are similar in
324 fresh and in used catalysts, i.e., Ru dispersion remains stable during reaction, except for the 5%
325 Ru sample.

326 Figures 5a and 5b show X-ray photoelectronic spectra corresponding to the nickel 2p_{3/2}
327 transition for fresh and used Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts, respectively. Deconvolutions of spectra were
328 carried out, since in all cases broad and asymmetric bands were observed, suggesting the
329 presence of different Ni species on the surface. Additionally, dashed black auxiliary lines were

330 included in the graphs, which indicate the energies described in the literature for different
331 nickel species. [29, 30]

332

FIGURE 5

333 All these catalysts exhibit peaks close to 856.0 and 858.0 eV with its corresponding shake-up
334 satellites at ~ 862.0 and ~ 864.5 eV. Note that the first peak is located among 853.9 and 857.0
335 eV, binding energies assigned to bulk NiO and NiAl₂O₄, respectively [31]. From this observation,
336 we can discard the presence of great amount of bulk NiO on all catalysts. The main peak at 856
337 eV corresponds to Ni²⁺ interacting with alumina [32], while the smaller peak at 858 eV is
338 consistent with the formation of nickel spinel NiAl₂O₄ [28]. On the one hand, the slight shift of
339 the main peak towards higher BE with the increase of Ni content could be due to the
340 weakening of metal-support interaction [33]. On the other hand, the main peak remains in the
341 same position after reaction, indicating that Ni species are stable during catalytic tests. It
342 should also be mentioned that no Ni⁰ specie was found in used catalysts (Figure 5b), since its
343 passivation occurs when the samples are in contact with air.

344 Ru 3d_{5/2} core level XPS spectra of fresh and used Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts are displayed in Figures 6a
345 and 6b, respectively. As in the case of Ni catalysts, auxiliary dashed black lines indicating
346 reported energies of different Ru species were included in the figures. XPS spectra of fresh
347 catalysts with different content of Ru can be deconvoluted into two contributions assignable
348 to two species of Ru, both cationic, at ~ 282.3 and ~ 280.8 eV. These peaks are consistent with
349 the presence of Ru(VI) and Ru(IV) oxides on the surface of the catalysts [34, 35]. The XPS
350 spectra of used catalysts exhibit the partial reduction of ruthenium oxides during the catalytic
351 tests, showing two peaks at ~ 281.4 and ~ 280.0 eV. In this case, these peaks correspond to
352 hydrated RuO₂ and metallic Ru, respectively [36, 37]. Finally, the long tail observed at binding
353 energies higher than 282 eV is due to overlap with C 1s transition.

354

FIGURE 6

355 H₂-TPR experiments were carried out in order to analyze the reduction state of Ni and Ru
356 species dispersed on alumina but also to determine the effect of metal loading over the
357 reducibility of the prepared catalysts. Figures 7a and 7b show H₂-TPR profiles of fresh Ni/Al₂O₃
358 and Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts, respectively. First of all, differences in redox properties are evident: the
359 complete reduction of nickel-based catalyst is only achieved by increasing the temperature up
360 to 900 °C, whereas only 250 °C are required for ruthenium loaded catalysts. These distinct
361 redox properties could be translated in different catalytic performances, since it is well known

362 that both active sites (Ni or Ru) must be reduced to carry out the hydrogenation of CO₂
363 efficiently.

364

FIGURE 7

365 With the aim of characterizing the type of nickel and ruthenium species presented in alumina
366 supported catalysts, H₂-TPR profiles were deconvoluted applying Gaussian-type deconvolution.
367 H₂-TPR profiles displayed in Figure 7a present 3 deconvoluted H₂ consumption peaks
368 assignable to three different Ni species, named α , β and γ [14, 33, 38]. The peak located at the
369 lowest temperature, close to 550 °C, is attributed to reduction of α -type NiO, weakly
370 interacting with alumina. The second peak centered at 670 °C, however, is assigned to
371 reduction of β -type NiO with stronger interaction with the support [28, 39]. Finally, the peak at
372 the highest temperature, with maximum located close to 780 °C, is assigned to reduction of γ -
373 type Ni specie forming well dispersed NiAl₂O₄ structure, in line with the results observed by
374 thermo XRD study and XPS. Note that, in accordance with previous XPS results, H₂-TPR profiles
375 shift to lower temperatures with increasing of Ni content, which is related to weakening of
376 metal-support interaction already reported by other authors [24].

377 Relative amounts of Ni species together with reducibility percentages and H₂/Ni ratios are
378 summarized in Table 3. Note that the relative amount of α -type NiO grows progressively with
379 Ni loading, increasing from 8% (4%Ni/Al₂O₃) up to 44% (20%Ni/Al₂O₃), whereas the amount of
380 γ -type NiO decreases from 62 to 14%. Additionally, in order to determine the amount of nickel
381 reducible at 500 °C, additional H₂-TPR tests were run up to 500 °C, for 1 h and under 20% H₂/Ar
382 (TPR profiles included in Figure S3). As expected, the percentage of nickel reducible at 500 °C
383 increased from 10 to 56% with Ni loading, confirming the mentioned slight weakening of
384 metal-support interaction and indicating that in no case will all nickel be reduced during
385 reaction. Finally, note that the H₂/Ni ratio is close to 1 in all cases, which indicates, as
386 previously observed in XPS characterization, that Ni²⁺ is the only specie reducible, according to
387 the following reduction step: NiO + H₂ → Ni + H₂O .

388

TABLE 3

389 Figure 7b shows deconvoluted H₂-TPR profiles of Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts. All catalysts exhibit a main
390 H₂ consumption peak with a maximum located at 210 °C, a shoulder at 190 °C and one
391 additional smaller peak, whose reduction starts above 140 °C. On the one hand, the main peak
392 is attributed to reduction of supported RuO₂ into metallic Ru [40–42], whereas the mentioned
393 shoulder at lower temperature is due to reduction of well dispersed RuO_x species [43, 44].

394 Then, the peak at lowest temperature peak could be related to reduction of RuO₃, as already
395 observed in XPS results.

396 From integration of H₂-TPR signal, total H₂ consumptions, RuO₃/RuO₂ ratios and H₂/Ru ratios
397 were calculated and included in Table 3. RuO₃/RuO₂ ratios are between 0.17 and 0.24, i.e., all
398 catalysts present similar and considerably higher relative amounts of RuO₂ than of RuO₃.
399 Finally, it should be noted that H₂/Ru molar ratios are between 2.2 and 2.3 (value slightly
400 higher than required for RuO₂ reduction), which confirms the presence of RuO₂ and trace
401 amounts of RuO₃, according to the following reduction step: RuO_x + xH₂ → Ru + xH₂O (x=2,3).

402 3.2. CO₂ methanation

403 The performance of catalysts was evaluated by analyzing CO₂ conversions and CH₄ yields. In all
404 cases, CO was the only secondary product and carbon balance closed within ± 5%. The catalytic
405 activity at different temperatures as a function of the Ni and Ru loading is shown in Figures 8a
406 and 8b, respectively. First of all, as it can be clearly observed, the increase of metal content
407 results in an enhancement of catalytic activity and, generally, a higher temperature provides a
408 higher CO₂ conversion. However, slight decrease of CO₂ conversion is observed at
409 temperatures above 400 °C in cases where conversions close to that of equilibrium are
410 obtained, as expected for exothermic reactions. Regarding Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts (Figure 8a), the
411 onset temperature for CO₂ methanation is around 250 °C, the highest CO₂ conversions are
412 achieved close to 450 °C for catalysts with Ni contents higher than 8% ($X_{\text{CO}_2} \approx 85\%$) and
413 equilibrium CO₂ conversion is only reached above 475 °C for 20%Ni/Al₂O₃. Noteworthy, the
414 temperature at which 50% CO₂ conversion is obtained (T_{50}) is reduced in 127 °C when
415 increasing the Ni loading from 4 to 20% ($T_{50} = 443$ °C and $T_{50} = 316$ °C, respectively). In the
416 same way, catalysts with Ni nominal loadings above 12% provide similar CO₂ conversion values
417 ($X_{\text{CO}_2} \approx 80\%$) when reaction temperatures rises over 400 °C. Therefore, it can be concluded that
418 12% Ni loading and a metallic surface of 5.1 m² g⁻¹ is sufficient to provide enough active sites
419 (Ni⁰) in order to achieve high CO₂ conversions at intermediate-high temperatures.

420

FIGURE 8

421 Analogously, Figure 8b shows the influence of temperature on catalytic performance of
422 Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts. In this case, higher CO₂ conversions are observed at low temperatures (T <
423 300 °C) in comparison with Ni based catalysts. Maximum CO₂ conversion is reached, regardless
424 the Ru content, at 400 °C, being also around 85% for catalysts with high metal content. Taking
425 into account that the variation of Ru loading is much lower, similar T_{50} reduction, as compared
426 to Ni catalysts, is obtained: from 396 °C (1% Ru) to 310 °C (5% Ru). Note that, in line with Ni

427 based catalysts, a higher metal loading provides greater activity and that the same saturation
428 effect is observed, obtaining almost similar (or even lower) CO₂ conversions for catalysts with
429 nominal Ru contents above 4% (metal surface of 0.61 m² g⁻¹). This is the minimum nominal
430 content needed to achieve at least 80% CO₂ conversion above 350 °C. Hence, the impregnation
431 of Ru loading higher than 4% can be considered unnecessary, since no further enhancement in
432 activity is observed.

433 In Figure 9, CH₄ yields of 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ and 4%Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts are compared at 300, 350 and
434 400 °C. It can be noticed that increasing temperature leads to higher Y_{CH_4} (highest CH₄
435 productions are observed at 400 °C) and that 4%Ru/Al₂O₃ is notably more productive than
436 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst, in line with the upgrade in CO₂ conversions observed in Figure 8. In fact,
437 regardless the studied temperature, Ru containing catalyst produces more methane than Ni
438 based catalyst (35% vs. 15% at 300 °C, 80% vs. 55% at 350 °C and 85% vs. 77% at 400 °C).
439 Noteworthy, CO yields lower than 1% were observed for 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst and negligible
440 trace amounts of CO were produced by 4%Ru/Al₂O₃ catalyst.

441

FIGURE 9

442 The activity of alumina supported 12% Ni and 4%Ru catalysts was compared with other state-
443 of-art materials recently reported in literature, including commercial samples [8, 18, 22, 24, 45,
444 46]. Table 4 includes the catalysts composition together with the main operational
445 parameters, i.e. H₂/CO₂ molar ratio and W/F_{A0} . As can be observed, the main operational
446 parameters differ from each other, and thus, the comparison is not straightforward. Although
447 12Ni/Al catalyst developed in this work presents a somewhat higher T_{50} , nickel loading is
448 significantly lower with respect to other reported samples. Furthermore, the W/F_{A0} used in this
449 study is the lowest, i.e. a lower amount of catalyst is used to treat the inlet feedstream. On the
450 other hand, the 4Ru/Al sample developed in this work presents a similar T_{50} to that reported
451 for other samples. Again, the T_{50} was evaluated in more demanding experimental conditions,
452 with the lowest W/F_{A0} . Taking all this considerations into account, it can be concluded that the
453 catalytic performance of Ni and Ru based catalysts prepared in this work is comparable to
454 other state-of-art materials, including commercial samples.

455

TABLE 4

456 3.3. Activation energies and catalysts stability

457 To determine apparent activation energies in the absence of catalyst deactivation (no C
458 deposition) the intermediate temperature region, from 275 to 335 °C, was chosen. Because
459 differential reactor conditions were difficult to achieve at higher temperatures, the initial

460 reaction rates approach was employed instead. Measurements of the catalytic performance at
 461 varying space-time (Figure 10a and 10b) allowed fitting conversion vs. space-time curves,
 462 which its extrapolation at $W / F_{CO_2}^0 = 0$, and corresponding derivatives results in values of initial
 463 reaction rates at every temperature,

$$464 \quad -r_{CO_2}^0 = r_{CH_4} = \left(\frac{dX_{CO_2}}{d(W / F_{CO_2}^0)} \right)_{W / F_{CO_2}^0 = 0} = k_{ap} f(C_{CO_2}^0, C_{H_2}^0) \quad (5)$$

465 that together with the Arrhenius expression

$$466 \quad k_{ap} = A_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{ap}}{RT}\right) \quad (6)$$

$$467 \quad \ln(-r_{CO_2}^0) = \ln\left[A_0 f(C_{CO_2}^0, C_{H_2}^0)\right] - \frac{E_{ap}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T}\right) \quad (7)$$

468 allows determination of the apparent activation energy from the slope of linear plot of
 469 $\ln(-r_{CO_2}^0)$ vs. $1/T$ (Equation 7), as represented in Figure 10c and 10d for 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ and
 470 4%Ru/Al₂O₃, respectively.

471 **FIGURE 10**

472 With the aim of comparing activity of catalysts with different nature of the metal active phase,
 473 also turnover frequencies (*TOF*), defined as an intrinsic reaction rate referred to molar surface
 474 metal active site (from H₂ chemisorption results, Table 2), have been calculated (Equation 8),
 475 resulting in values reported in Table 5.

$$476 \quad TOF_{Me} (s^{-1}) = \frac{-r_{CO_2}^0, \text{ mol CO}_2 (\text{g cat.})^{-1} s^{-1}}{S_{Me}, \text{ mol Me (g cat.)}^{-1}} \quad (\text{Me=Ni,Ru}) \quad (8)$$

477 Note that, disregarded of Ni or Ru catalysts, *TOF* increases exponentially with temperature,
 478 with one order of magnitude higher for Ru/Al₂O₃ than Ni/Al₂O₃ in the range of temperature
 479 from 275 to 300 °C. This clearly indicates that ruthenium is much more effective metal for CO₂
 480 methanation than nickel.

481 **TABLE 5**

482 From these initial reaction rates values and applying Arrhenius equation, apparent activation
 483 energies were calculated for both formulations (Figure 10c and 10d). The apparent activation
 484 energy for CO₂ methanation resulted to be 129 kJ mol⁻¹ over Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst and 84 kJ mol⁻¹
 485 over Ru/Al₂O₃ catalyst. The determination of activation energy values has already been

486 conducted by other authors, observing similar values that ranges 60-80 kJ mol⁻¹ on Ru/Al₂O₃
487 catalysts [16, 20, 46] and 95-120 kJ mol⁻¹ on Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts [45, 48]. The observed notable
488 difference in activation energy (45 kJ mol⁻¹) is related to differences in reaction mechanism: it
489 is known that noble metals are more effective in H₂ dissociation than non-noble and that may
490 explain the lower activation energy observed for Ru/Al₂O₃. In fact, Dreyer et al. [47] have
491 reported that the presence of H₂ adsorption sites is essential for efficient CH₄ formation.

492 Despite the high reaction heat of CO₂ methanation ($\Delta H = -165$ kJ mol⁻¹), it should be noted that
493 both Anderson criterion [49] and Mears criterion [50] were satisfied, indicating an absence of
494 internal and external temperature gradients during catalytic runs for determination of
495 activation energies (Table S1).

496 Finally, the stability of catalysts with the optimum metal contents (12%Ni/Al₂O₃ and
497 4%Ru/Al₂O₃) was studied for 24h-on-stream at 350 °C. Interestingly, a slight increase in the CO₂
498 conversion was observed for 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst in Figure 11a. The CO₂ conversion of
499 4%Ru/Al₂O₃, in contrast, slightly decreased from 81.5 to 78.0% (Figure 11b). Ni and Ru based
500 catalysts were characterized by TG and TEM after 24h-on-stream. Thermogravimetric studies
501 carried out under 5%O₂/He flow showed no relevant mass losses when increasing temperature
502 up to 850 °C (Figure S4), indicating that no carbon deposits were formed during stability tests
503 at 350 °C and under a gas stream with high H₂ concentration. By means of TEM (Figure S5),
504 average particle sizes of 6 and 7 nm were estimated for fresh and used Ni catalysts,
505 respectively, which reveals a slight particle sintering during the stability test. The same
506 conclusion was extracted for Ru based catalysts. The average particle size was 24 and 28 nm
507 for fresh and used catalysts, respectively.

508 In the case of Ni based catalysts, the slight particle sintering seems to be compensated by the
509 activation of additional nickel species and reduction of nickel oxide with high interaction with
510 the alumina. On the other hand, as Ru is completely reduced before the catalytic test, the
511 slight sintering of Ru particles results in a decrease of the CO₂ conversion during the stability
512 test. It is worth to mention that in both cases the selectivity to methane kept stable, obtaining
513 values higher than 98% (Figures 11c y 11d).

514 **FIGURE 11**

515

516 **4. Conclusions**

517 In this work, a series of alumina-supported Ni and Ru catalysts were prepared by wetness
518 incipient impregnation varying the metal content, characterized by multiple techniques (N₂-

519 physisorption, CO₂-TPD, XRD, XPS and H₂-TPR) and evaluated for CO₂ methanation. The main
520 conclusions are listed as follows:

521 According to basicity results (CO₂-TPD), the impregnation of increasing loading of Ni and Ru
522 results in the formation of new basic sites suggesting that both active phases are able to
523 adsorb CO₂, which is an essential step in CO₂ methanation mechanism. Nevertheless, the
524 different strength of those new basic sites indicates the presence of various species of
525 adsorbed CO₂.

526 XRD results revealed that alumina supported Ru crystals tend to grow and agglomerate into
527 larger particles with increasing of calcination temperature, resulting in lower metal dispersion.
528 On the contrary, the increase of temperature does not affect Ni dispersion, but leads to the
529 formation of nickel phases with higher interaction with alumina, especially for catalysts with
530 low Ni content. According to H₂-chemisorption results, Ni dispersion decreases around 25% by
531 increasing Ni content from 4 to 20% due to the formation of larger NiO particles. However,
532 unlike for Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts, the dispersion of Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts is not significantly influenced
533 by metal loading.

534 The reducibility of the active phase, linked to metal-support interaction, seemed to be a key
535 factor. The reduction of alumina supported Ru is complete at low temperature ($T < 300$ °C),
536 while alumina supported Ni is not completely reduced at 500 °C. This indicates that all Ru but
537 not all Ni will be available to dissociate hydrogen during reaction. The reducibility is even lesser
538 for catalysts with low Ni content due to a higher metal-support interaction, in accordance with
539 XPS and H₂-TPR results.

540 Considering the saturation effect of CO₂ conversion with metal loading, 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ ($T_{50} = 340$
541 °C) and 4%Ru/Al₂O₃ ($T_{50} = 310$ °C) were the best formulations, providing maximum CO₂
542 conversions of 80 and 85% around 425 and 375 °C, respectively and being quite stable for 24h-
543 on-stream. The TOF values for Ru/Al₂O₃ catalyst were considerably higher than those observed
544 for Ni/Al₂O₃ at low temperature ($T < 300$ °C), since ruthenium is more effective in H₂
545 dissociation/adsorption than nickel, which is another fundamental step of reaction
546 mechanism.

547

548 **Acknowledgments**

549 The support from the Economy and Competitiveness Spanish Ministry (CTQ2015-67597-C2-1-R
550 and CTQ2015-67597-C2-2-R MINECO-FEDER), the Basque Government (IT657-13 and IT1297-
551 19) and the SGIker (Analytical Services) at the University of the Basque Country are
552 acknowledged. One of the authors (AQ) also acknowledges University of the Basque Country
553 by his PhD grant (PIF-15/351).

554

555 **Nomenclature**

556	d_p	Catalyst particle diameter, mm
557	d_{pore}	Mean pore diameter, nm
558	E_{ap}	Apparent activation energy, kJ mol^{-1}
559	F_i	Molar flow of component i, mol h^{-1}
560	$GSVH$	Gas hour space velocity, h^{-1}
561	$-r_{\text{CO}_2}^0$	Initial reaction rate, $\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ h}^{-1} (\text{g cat.})^{-1}$
562	R	Ideal gas constant, $\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
563	S_{BET}	Specific surface, $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$
564	S_{Me}	Metal surface, $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$
565	T	Temperature, K
566	T_{50}	Temperature for 50% CO_2 conversion, $^{\circ}\text{C}$
567	TOF	Turnover frequency, s^{-1}
568	V_{meso}	Mesopore volume, $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$
569	W	Catalyst weight, g
570	$W / F_{\text{CO}_2}^0$	Space-time, $(\text{g cat.}) \text{h mol}^{-1}$
571	X_{CO_2}	Carbon dioxide conversion, %
572	Y_{CH_4}	Methane yield, %
573	Y_{CO}	Carbon monoxide yield, %

574

575 **References**

- 576 [1] B. K. Sovacool, How long will it take? Conceptualizing the temporal dynamics of energy
577 transitions. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 13 (2016) 202–215.
- 578 [2] A. A. Olajire. Valorization of greenhouse carbon dioxide emissions into value-added
579 products by catalytic processes. *J. CO₂ Util.* 3–4 (2013) 74–92.
- 580 [3] C. Song. Global challenges and strategies for control, conversion and utilization of CO₂ for
581 sustainable development involving energy, catalysis, adsorption and chemical processing.
582 *Catal. Today* 115 (2006) 2–32.
- 583 [4] W. Wang and J. Gong. Methanation of carbon dioxide: an overview. *Front. Chem. Sci. Eng.*
584 5(1) (2011) 2–10.
- 585 [5] F. Ocampo, B. Louis, A.-C. Roge. Methanation of carbon dioxide over nickel-based
586 Ce_{0.72}Zr_{0.28}O₂ mixed oxide catalysts prepared by sol-gel method. *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* 369 (2009)
587 90–96.
- 588 [6] F. Ocampo, B. Louis, L. Kiwi-Minsker, A.-C. Roge. Effect of Ce/Zr composition and noble
589 metal promotion on nickel based Ce_xZr_{1-x}O₂ catalysts for carbon dioxide methanation. *Appl.*
590 *Catal. A Gen.* 392 (2011) 36–44.
- 591 [7] M. Romero-Sáez, L.Y. Jaramillo, W. Henao, U. de la Torre. *Emerging Nanostructured*
592 *Materials for Energy and Environmental Science* (2018), Springer.
593 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04474-9>.
- 594 [8] G. Garbarino, D. Bellotti, P. Riani, L. Magistri, G. Busca. Methanation of carbon dioxide on
595 Ru/Al₂O₃ and Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts at atmospheric pressure: Catalysts activation, behavior and
596 stability. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 40 (2015) 9171–9182.
- 597 [9] S. Abate, C. Mebrahtu, E. Giglio, F. Deorsola, S. Bensaid, S. Perathoner, R. Pirone, G. Centi.
598 Catalytic Performance of γ-Al₂O₃-ZrO₂-TiO₂-CeO₂ composite oxide supported Ni-Based Catalysts
599 for CO₂ methanation. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 55 (2016) 4451–4460.
- 600 [10] X. Su, J. Xu, B. Liang, H. Duan, B. Hou, Y. Huang. Catalytic carbon dioxide hydrogenation to
601 methane: A review of recent studies. *J. Energy Chem.* 25 (2016) 553–565.
- 602 [11] S. Rahmani, M. Rezaei, F. Meshkani. Preparation of promoted nickel catalysts supported
603 on mesoporous nanocrystalline gamma alumina for carbon dioxide methanation reaction. *J.*
604 *Ind. Eng. Chem.* (2014) 4176–4182.

- 605 [12] Q. Liu, F. Gu, X. Lu, Y. Liu, H. Li, Z. Zhong, G. Xu, F. Su. Enhanced catalytic performances of
606 Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst via addition of V₂O₃ for CO methanation. *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* 488 (2014) 37–
607 47.
- 608 [13] D. Pandey, G. Deo. Effect of support on the catalytic activity of supported Ni-Fe catalysts
609 for the CO₂ methanation reaction. *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* 33 (2016) 99–107.
- 610 [14] F. Song, Q. Zhong, Y. Yu, M. Shi, Y. Wu, J. Hu, Y. Song. Obtaining well-dispersed Ni/Al₂O₃
611 catalyst for CO₂ methanation with a microwave-assisted method. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 42
612 (2017) 4174–4183.
- 613 [15] D. Wierzbicki, R. Baran, R. Debek, M. Motak, T. Grzybek, M. E. Gálvez, P. Da Costa. The
614 influence of nickel content on the performance of hydrotalcite-derived catalysts in CO₂
615 methanation reaction. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 42 (2017) 23548–23555.
- 616 [16] J. H. Kwak, L. Kovarik, J. Szanyi. CO₂ reduction on supported Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts: cluster size
617 dependence of product selectivity. *ACS Catal.* 3 (2013) 2449–2455.
- 618 [17] C. Janke, M.S. Duyar, M. Hoskins, R. Farrauto. Catalytic and adsorption studies for the
619 hydrogenation of CO₂ to methane. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 152–153 (2014) 184–191.
- 620 [18] S. Tada, O. J. Ochieng, R. Kikuchi, T. Haneda, H. Kameyama. Promotion of CO₂ methanation
621 activity and CH₄ selectivity at low temperatures over Ru/CeO₂/Al₂O₃ catalysts. *Int. J. Hydrogen*
622 *Energy* 39 (2014) 10090–10100.
- 623 [19] S. Toemen, W. A. W. Abu Bakar, R. Ali. Effect of ceria and strontia over Ru/Mn/Al₂O₃
624 catalyst: Catalytic methanation, physicochemical and mechanistic studies. *J. CO₂ Util.* 13 (2016)
625 38–49.
- 626 [20] G. Garbarino, D. Bellotti, E. Finocchio, L. Magistri, G. Busca. Methanation of carbon dioxide
627 on Ru/Al₂O₃: Catalytic activity and infrared study. *Catal. Today* 277 (2016) 21–28.
- 628 [21] A. Quindimil, U. De-La-Torre, B. Pereda-Ayo, José A. González-Marcos, Juan R. González-
629 Velasco. Ni catalysts with La as promoter supported over Y- and BETA- zeolites for CO₂
630 methanation. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 218 (2018) 393–403.
- 631 [22] G. Garbarino, C. Wang, T. Cavattoni, E. Finocchio, P. Riani, M. Flytzani-Stephanopoulos, G.
632 Busca. A study of Ni/La-Al₂O₃ catalysts: A competitive system for CO₂ methanation. *Appl.*
633 *Catal. A Gen.* 248 (2019) 286–297.

- 634 [23] I. Iglesias, A. Quindimil, F. Mariño, U. De-La-Torre, Juan R. González-Velasco. Zr promotion
635 effect in CO₂ methanation over ceria supported nickel catalysts. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 44
636 (2019) 1710-1719.
- 637 [24] R. Darouhegi, F. Meshkani, M. Rezaei. Enhanced activity of CO₂ methanation over
638 mesoporous nanocrystalline Ni-Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared by ultrasound-assisted co-
639 precipitation method. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 42 (2017) 15115–15125.
- 640 [25] D. Wierzbicki, R. Debek, M. Motak, T. Grzybek, M. E. Gálvez, P. Da Costa. Novel Ni-La-
641 hydrotalcite derived catalysts for CO₂ methanation. *Catal. Commun.* 83 (2016) 5–8.
- 642 [26] R. Debek, M. Radlik, M. Motak, M. E. Galvez, W. Tureik, P. Da Costa, T. Grzybek. Ni-
643 containing Ce-promoted hydrotalcite derived materials as catalysts for methane reforming
644 with carbon dioxide at low temperature – On the effect of basicity. *Catal. Today* 257 (2015)
645 59–65.
- 646 [27] Z. Boukha, C. Jiménez-González, M. Gil-Calvo, B. de Rivas, J.R. González-Velasco, J. I.
647 Gutiérrez-Ortiz, R. López-Fonseca. MgO/NiAl₂O₄ as a new formulation of reforming catalysts:
648 Tuning the surface properties for the enhanced partial oxidation of methane. *Appl. Catal. B*
649 *Environ.* 199 (2016) 372–383.
- 650 [28] Z. Boukha, C. Jiménez-González, B de Rivas, J.R. González-Velasco, J. I. Gutiérrez-Ortiz, R.
651 López-Fonseca. Synthesis, characterization and performance evaluation of spinel-derived
652 Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts for various methane reforming reactions. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 158–159
653 (2014) 190–201.
- 654 [29] E. Heracleous, A.F. Lee, K. Wilson, A.A. Lemonidou. Investigation of Ni-based alumina-
655 supported catalysts for the oxidative dehydrogenation of ethane to ethylene: structural
656 characterization and reactivity studies. *J. Catal.* 231 (2005) 159–171.
- 657 [30] Hui Li, Hexing Li, Wei-Lin Dai, Weijiang Wang, Zhigang Fang, Jing-Fa Deng. XPS studies on
658 surface electronic characteristics of Ni–B and Ni–P amorphous alloy and its correlation to their
659 catalytic properties. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 152 (1999) 25–34.
- 660 [31] C. Heine, B. A. J. Lechner, H. Bluhm, M. Salmeron. Recycling of CO: Probing the chemical
661 state of the Ni(111) surface during the methanation reaction with ambient pressure X-ray
662 photoelectron spectroscopy. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 138(40) (2016) 13246–13252.
- 663 [32] H.-W. Kim, K.-M. Kang, H.-Y. Kwak, J. H. Kim. Preparation of supported Ni catalysts on
664 various metal oxides with core/shell structures and their tests for the steam reforming of
665 methane. *Chem. Eng. J.* 168 (2011) 775–783.

666 [33] C. Jiménez-González, Z. Boukha, B. de Rivas, J. J. Delgado, M. A. Cauqui, J. R. González-
667 Velasco, J. I. Gutiérrez-Ortiz, R. López-Fonseca. Structural characterisation of Ni/alumina
668 reforming catalysts activated at high temperature. *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* 466 (2013) 9–20.

669 [34] K.S. Kim and N. Winograd. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopic studies of ruthenium-oxygen
670 surfaces. *J. Catal.* 35 (1974) 66–72.

671 [35] S. Kawi, S. Y. Liu, S.-C. Shen. Catalytic decomposition and reduction of N₂O on Ru/MCM-41
672 catalyst. *Catal. Today* 68 (2001) 237–244.

673 [36] K. Qadir, S. H. Joo, B. S. Mun, D. R. Butcher, J. R. Renzas, F. Aksoy, Z. Liu, G. A. Somorjai, J.
674 Y. Park. Intrinsic relation between catalytic activity of CO oxidation on Ru nanoparticles and Ru
675 oxides uncovered with ambient pressure XPS. *Nano Lett.* 12 (2012) 5761–5768.

676 [37] S. Carencó, C. Sassoie, M. Faustini, P. Eloy, D. P. Debecker, H. Bluhm, M. B. Salmeron. The
677 Active State of Supported Ruthenium Oxide Nanoparticles during Carbon Dioxide
678 Methanation. *J. Phys. Chem. C* 120(28) (2016) 15354–15361.

679 [38] A. Morales-Marín, J.L. Ayastuy, U. Iriarte-Velasco, M.A. Gutierrez-Ortiz. Nickel aluminate
680 spinel-derived catalysts for the aqueous phase reforming of glycerol: Effect of reduction
681 temperature. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 244 (2019) 931–945.

682 [39] K. Ray, G. Deo. A potential descriptor for the CO₂ hydrogenation to CH₄ over Al₂O₃
683 supported Ni and Ni-based alloy catalysts. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 218 (2017) 525–537.

684 [40] P. Betancourt, A. Rives, R. Hubaut, C.E. Scott, J. Goldwasser. A study of the ruthenium-
685 alumina system. *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* 170 (1998) 307–314.

686 [41] V. Mazzieri, F. Coloma-Pascual, A Arcoya, P.C. L'Argentièrre, N.S. Fígoli. XPS, FTIR and TPR
687 characterization of Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 210 (2003) 222–230.

688 [42] T. Mitsui, K. Tsutsui, T. Matsui, R. Kikuchi, K. Eguchi. Support effect on complete oxidation
689 of volatile organic compounds over Ru catalysts. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 81 (2008) 56–63.

690 [43] R. Lanza, S. G. Jaras, P. Canu. Partial oxidation of methane over supported ruthenium
691 catalysts. *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* 325 (2007) 57–67.

692 [44] K. Kousi, D.I. Kondarides, X.E. Verykios, C. Papadopoulou. Glycerol steam reforming over
693 modified Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts. *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* 542 (2017) 201–211.

694 [45] C. V. Miguel, A. Mendes, L.M. Madeira. Intrinsic kinetics of CO₂ methanation over an
695 industrial nickel-based catalyst. *J. CO₂ Util.* 25 (2018) 128–136.

696 [46] L. Falbo, M. Martinelli, C. G. Visconti, L. Lietti, C. Bassano, P. Deiana. Kinetics of CO₂
697 methanation on a Ru-based catalyst at process conditions relevant for Power-to-Gas
698 applications. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 225 (2018) 354-363.

699 [47] J. H. A. Dreyer, P. Li, L. Zhang, G. K. Beh, R. Zhang, P. H.-L. Sit, W. Y. Teoh. Influence of the
700 oxide support reducibility on the CO₂ methanation over Ru-based catalysts. *Appl. Catal. B*
701 *Environ.* 219 (2017) 715–726.

702 [48] T. Van Herwijnen, H. Van Doesburg, W.A. De Jong. Kinetics of the methanation of CO and
703 CO₂ on a nickel catalyst. *J. Catal.* 28 (1973) 391–402.

704 [49] J.B. Anderson. A criterion for isothermal behavior of catalyst pellet. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 18
705 (1963) 147-148.

706 [50] D. E. Mears. Tests for transport limitations in experimental catalytic reactors. *Ind. Eng.*
707 *Chem. Proc. Des. Dev.* 10 (1971) 541-547.

708

709 **TABLES AND FIGURES CAPTIONS**

710 **Table 1.** Physicochemical properties of alumina-supported Ni and Ru catalysts.

711 **Table 2.** Crystallite sizes and metal dispersions of the catalysts.

712 **Table 3.** Data from H₂-TPR studies of the impregnated Ni and Ru catalysts.

713 **Table 4.** Catalytic performance comparison among Ni and Ru based catalysts reported in
714 literature.

715 **Table 5.** Initial reaction rates and TOF values of 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ and 4%Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts.

716

717 **Figure 1.** CO₂-TPD profiles of γ -Al₂O₃ support, 20%Ni/Al₂O₃ and 5%Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts.

718 **Figure 2.** XRD patterns of reduced (a) alumina-supported Ni catalysts and (b) alumina-
719 supported Ru catalysts.

720 **Figure 3.** Thermodiffraction analysis of (a) 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ and (b) 4%Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts from
721 30 to 1010 °C.

722 **Figure 4.** Effect of (a) Ni and (b) Ru content on Ru/Al and Ni/Al surface atomic ratios.

723 **Figure 5.** Ni 2p_{3/2} XPS spectra of (a) fresh and (b) used catalysts.

724 **Figure 6.** Ru 2d_{5/2} XPS spectra of (a) fresh and (b) used catalysts.

725 **Figure 7.** H₂-TPR profiles of (a) Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts and (b) Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts.

726 **Figure 8.** CO₂ conversion as a function of reaction temperature for (a) Ni/Al₂O₃ and (b)
727 Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts.

728 **Figure 9.** C-species distribution of 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ and 4%Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts at 300, 350 and 400
729 °C.

730 **Figure 10.** Effect of W/F_{A0} on CO₂ conversion for (a) 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ and (b) 4%Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts
731 together with Arrhenius plots (c and d).

732 **Figure 11.** Evolution of CO₂ conversion and selectivity to CH₄/CO at 350 °C with time-on-stream
733 over 24h for (a) 12%Ni/Al₂O₃ and (b) 4%Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts.

734

735

TABLE 1

736

Sample	Ni/Al and Ru/Al ^a	S_{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	V_{meso} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	d_{pore} (nm)	Desorbed CO ₂ ^b , μmol g ⁻¹	Basicity (μmol CO ₂ m ⁻²)
Al ₂ O ₃	-	214	0.563	10.1	69	0.32
4%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	0.038	191	0.435	8.8	80	0.42
8%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	0.079	175	0.383	8.4	72	0.41
12%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	0.122	160	0.373	9.0	71	0.44
16%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	0.175	147	0.369	9.7	68	0.46
20%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	0.224	131	0.326	9.6	65	0.50
1%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	0.007	198	0.411	8.0	71	0.36
2%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	0.015	193	0.429	8.4	74	0.38
3%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	0.021	185	0.417	8.5	69	0.37
4%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	0.029	172	0.382	8.5	67	0.39
5%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	0.032	179	0.425	9.1	75	0.42

^a Determined by XRF.^b Calculated from CO₂-TPD profiles.

737

738

739

740

TABLE 2

741

Catalyst	Crystallite size (nm) ^a		Dispersion (%) ^b	Metal surface (m ² g ⁻¹)
	NiO or RuO ₂	Ni or Ru		
4%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	< 5	< 5	38.3	0.985
8%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	< 5	< 5	26.1	2.907
12%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	< 5	4.8	17.9	5.083
16%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	9	6.1	13.3	6.186
20%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	8.5	7.3	11.0	7.527
1%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	29.0	7.4	5.5	0.201
2%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	34.0	8.1	4.7	0.344
3%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	37.9	11.0	4.5	0.489
4%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	41.4	11.3	4.2	0.609
5%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	43.8	12.1	3.9	0.711

742

^aEstimated by Scherrer equation.

743

^bCalculated by H₂-chemisorption.

744

745

746

TABLE 3

747

Catalyst	Total H ₂ uptake (mmol g ⁻¹)	Ni Cont. ^a (wt.%)	Species (%)			H ₂ /Ni	Reducibility ^b (%)
			α	β	γ		
4%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	0.65	3.8	8	30	62	1.01	10
8%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	1.26	7.4	18	52	30	0.97	22
12%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	1.86	10.9	23	60	17	0.97	38
16%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	2.52	14.8	38	44	18	0.99	47
20%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	3.16	18.5	45	41	14	1.01	56

Catalyst	Total H ₂ uptake (mmol g ⁻¹)	Ru Cont. (%)	RuO ₃ /RuO ₂ ratio	H ₂ /Ru	Reducibility (%)
1%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	0.23	1.1	0.17	2.32	100
2%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	0.45	2.1	0.23	2.27	100
3%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	0.66	3.1	0.18	2.22	100
4%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	0.93	4.3	0.24	2.35	100
5%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	1.08	5.1	0.18	2.18	100

^aDetermined from integration of H₂-TPR profiles.

^bReduction conditions: 500 °C for 1h under 20%H₂/Ar. For these calculations Ni(II) has been assumed.

748

749

750

751

752

TABLE 4

753

Composition	Description	H ₂ /CO ₂ ratio	$W / F_{\text{CO}_2}^0$ (g h mol ⁻¹)	T ₅₀ , °C	Reference
12Ni/Al	Incipient wetness impregnation	5	5	340	This work
25NiO/Ca-Al	Comercial (METH134)	4	6	325	[45]
25Ni-Al	Co-precipitation	3.5	11	300	[24]
17NiO/14La/Al	Incipient wetness impregnation	5	8	280	[22]
4Ru/Al	Incipient wetness impregnation	5	5	310	This work
0.5Ru/Al	Commercial	4	25	300	[46]
3Ru/Al	Commercial	5	7	365	[8]
2Ru/30Ce/Al	Wet impregnation	4	11	285	[18]

754

755

TABLE 5

756

Catalyst	Temperature (°C)	$-r_{\text{CO}_2}^0$ (mmol h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹)	TOF (s ⁻¹)
12%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	275	27	0.06
	290	46	0.1
	305	87	0.19
	320	181	0.39
	335	446	0.95
4%Ru/Al ₂ O ₃	250	48	0.81
	265	69	1.16
	280	116	1.95
	295	217	3.65
	300	246	4.14

757

758

759

760

761

Figure 1
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 2
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 3

[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 4

[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 5
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 6
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 7
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 8
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 9

[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 10
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 11
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Supplementary Material

[Click here to download e-component: Supplementary Material_R1.docx](#)